

Interface Interaction Model

Luciane Maria Fadel

*Federal University of Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil, luciane_fadel@hotmail.com*

Abstract: This paper develops a theoretical model which describes means for increasing the number of interactions and for enhancing social presence in an online learning environment. This model considers Anderson's model of online learning and the variables indicated in the literature that might enhance social presence. These variables are: presence of others and response times. They were selected prioritising those that could affect the categories of indicators of social presence described by Garrison, Anderson and Archer. The model identifies three interface features that enhance social facilities: images, animation and text. Images, animation and text are used to portray social information while animation is used to present system feedback. In addition, this paper highlights the affective-motivational role of images, which might be crucial to students' satisfaction with the interface in an online course. Four experiments were designed to test and validate the corresponding concepts. The results show that the use of images, animation and text to portray information about the others fosters web mail and instant mail interaction among students. In addition, the use of animation providing system feedback to incoming messages contributes to an increase in the number of interactions.

Key words: *interface design, interaction model, communities of inquiry.*

1. Introduction

The interface design for social interaction might have a great effect on the students' perception of the others and on their own participation because the interface mediates all the interactions in an online learning environment. Although the computer as a medium has advantages (huge storage capacity, retrieval capability, easy geographical distribution of data), the interface design represents a bottleneck for current technology. One of the problems with the interface is crucial for online learning: enhancing social facilities.

This paper contextualises the research by discussing relevant literature that has shaped the motivation for conducting the research, the problem addressed, and the approach taken in this research. This paper is divided into five main sections. The first section explores the importance of interactions in communication among students in the context of an online learning course. In addition, this section addresses the challenges of defining social presence. The second section discusses the interaction and the communities of inquiry and discuss social presence as one of its core elements. The third section explores the variables that might enhance social presence. The fourth section contextualises the research problem by presenting the interface interaction model and discusses how interface design might enhance social facilities. This section argues for an exploration of how a

different interface design might be exploited to achieve maximum results in terms of students' perception of the others and participation. Last section discusses the results and points out future work.

2. Interaction

2.1. Definition of interaction

Interaction is defined by Wagner [1] as 'reciprocal events that require at least two objects and two actions. Interactions occur when these objects and events mutually influence one another'. In this paper, interaction is defined as message exchanged among students. It is assumed that the message is the agent that might influence the objects, in this case, the students. In fact, using Wagner's definition, interaction can be applied to different dimensions in an online learning environment, where the objects are mainly students, teachers and content. In an attempt to formalize its multi-faceted dimensions, Moore [2] listed three different modes of interaction in the online education context.

The modes of interactions listed by Moore [2] are labelled: student-content interaction, student-teacher interaction, and student-student interaction. Later Hillman, Willis and Gunawardena [3] considered the influence of the technology on the process of interacting, and presented the concept of student-interface interaction. A brief discussion of each of these models follows.

Student-content interaction is the interaction that results in understanding. This leads to an internal dialogue, a reflection about what was read or seen. This dialogue is the process in which students examine, consider and process the course information presented during the educational experience.

Student-teacher interaction is taken as being essential to learning independently both within face-to-face and online learning [15]. In both processes, the teacher is responsible for maintaining the student's interest and motivation [5].

The third mode of interaction, student-student interaction, is advocated by education theories that promote education in a social perspective [6,7]. Student-student interaction is crucial to establish the social setting for exchanging experiences and building knowledge. By interacting students are able to construct a deeper sense of an idea, which is the basis of a Community of Inquiry. A Community of Inquiry is based on mutual cooperation, open-ended questions, building on a range of viewpoints in an environment where all ideas are respected, and taking responsibility to think for oneself. Student-student interaction also motivates students and raises their interest [8]. This is mainly because of the perspectives taken into account in student-student interaction models as demonstrated by Slavin [9,10]. Slavin describes three approaches: motivational, social cohesion and cognitive approaches. Motivational Approaches focus on the reward mechanisms that suit students. Proponents of the motivational perspective argue that if students value the success of the group as a whole and are rewarded for this, they will encourage and help one another to achieve.

Social Cohesion Approaches emphasise social relations and are based largely on Dewey's [11] experiential philosophy, and generally emphasise intrinsic rather than extrinsic motivations. Intrinsic motivations lead students to help each other to learn because they care about each other and want each other to succeed.

The Cognitive Approaches identified by Slavin [10] hold that interactions among students will in themselves increase achievement. This is for reasons that have to do with the processing of information (rather than motivations), and therefore approaches that emphasise interactions are often referred to as 'cognitive'. One of the first cognitive models was described by Piaget [6]. Piaget noted that peer interactions provide the necessary

requirements for creating an atmosphere of ‘cognitive conflict’ because interaction forces students to explain, elaborate, and address alternative views with their peers. Similarly, social interaction and collaborative problem-solving were seen as crucial for the child’s development in Vygotsky’s [7] studies. A more recent cognitive perspective may be described as ‘cognitive elaboration’. Research in this area suggests that new information must be linked through a process of restructure or elaboration, with information already retained through memory [12]. One of the most effective means of elaboration is explaining information to someone else [13], and interaction with peers is essential in this context.

Another important contribution to understanding interaction in online education comes from Hillman, Willis and Gunawardena [3]. They described the student-interface interaction, which can be said to be the process of manipulating tools to accomplish a task. This is a critical point because this process probably will interfere with how much time the user will need to learn the tool. Hillman, Willis and Gunawardena also distinguished between student-interface interaction and the necessary mediation of an interface which occurs in any interaction, by noting that for the technically-challenged learner, the interface itself becomes ‘an independent force with which the learner must contend’. Their argumentation comes from the work of Salomon about the relationship between the medium and the message [14]. Salomon’s work is devoted to understanding of the use of media in education. He states that symbol systems partly determine who will acquire how much knowledge from what kinds of messages.

All forms of interactions in an online learning environment are, by definition, mediated forms of interaction. Therefore, the student-interface interaction is a component of each of the other forms of interaction whenever they occur in an online learning environment. Although acknowledging that the acquisition of communication and technical skills is crucial in the context of online learning, Anderson and Garrison [15] left the interaction with the interface out of their discussion. They expanded the discussion on interaction to include three other forms of interaction: teacher-teacher, teacher-content, and content-content. Considering now six modes of interaction, student-teacher, student-student, student-content, teacher-content, teacher-teacher, and content-content interaction, and investigating his own distance teaching, Anderson [8] proposed an interaction-based model of learning as follows.

2.3. Model of e-learning

Anderson [16] developed the interaction model of e-learning based on his interaction equivalency theorem. The interaction equivalency theorem implies that a distance course designer can substitute one type of interaction for one of the others with little loss in education effectiveness. This model incorporates all six types of interaction in an expansive framework, which covers a variety of online learning models including independent study and paced collaborative learning. The interaction-based model of e-learning illustrates the two major human actors – students and teachers, and their interactions with each other and with the content. Students and teachers can interact among themselves and interact directly with the content.

This model helps to evaluate how much of the educational process is composed of interaction with non-human entities, and how much with human-human interaction. The balance is not easily achieved but it is being developed through reflective discourse among researchers and online learning practitioners.

Anderson [16] envisions that the high cost student-teacher interaction will be substituted with increased student-student and student-content interaction. Students may choose to study independently and thus interact directly

with the content. For this kind of interaction with content, study materials such as tutorials, videos, simulations etc., are especially constructed to provide high levels of student-content interaction. Other students may choose a paced collaborative learning where the interactions with other students and the teacher are crucial. These interactions should take place in a Community of Inquiry using synchronous and/or asynchronous interaction.

This paper focuses on the design of social facilities that might encourage students to interact. Therefore, the environments created as research prototypes considered mainly student-student interactions (a paced collaborative learning) embedded in a Community of Inquiry with the majority of the lectures delivered online and a few face-to-face meetings. Interactions use text, and are considered to be messages exchanged between students. The Community of Inquiry framework was used to design the online courses for the experiments and it is described next.

3. The model of a community of inquiry

Community of Inquiry theory is rooted in pragmatism, a tradition of philosophy and social action which views knowledge as emergent, communally constructed, and a melding of creativity and critical thinking. Community of Inquiry theory is underpinned by a long tradition of scholarship and social action in work by Charles S. Peirce, William James, John Dewey and Jane Addams. The key description marking out the Community of Inquiry is a group (or social setting) of individuals who use dialogue to solve problems. This group is strongly linked, even in a virtual world, socially and cognitively. Therefore the three elements that form the core of the model of a Community of Inquiry developed by Garrison, Anderson and Archer [17] are: teaching presence, cognitive presence and social presence.

The presence of the teacher is crucial in supporting a community and in balancing cognitive and social issues so they are consistent with the intended learning outcomes. Teaching presence can include designing and managing learning sequences, providing subject matter expertise and facilitating active learning.

Cognitive presence is related to the students' ability to construct meaning through sustained communication. It is grounded in critical thinking literature. Critical thinking requires that students actively assimilate knowledge based on their own experiences and previous knowledge.

Social presence is defined as the extent to which the virtual entities that represent others are perceived as real in an online environment. The perception comes through interactions between participants and the virtual representations of others. As explained before, interactions are considered to be messages exchanged among students. In addition, the degree of social presence is measured by investigating students' perceptions about group belonging and visual awareness.

4. Social presence

4.1. Social presence variables

The interface design used in the experiments enhanced two variables that affect social presence. They were selected prioritising those that could affect the categories of indicators of social presence described by Garrison, Anderson and Archer [17]. The variables are:

- **The presence of other people in the environment**, which is a media variable [18, 19]. The presence of others might enhance the sense of belonging, which affects another social presence category of

indicators, group cohesion [17]. To enhance the presence of others, experiment 3 investigated the use of images, animation and text to portray social information;

- **Response time**, which is related to interactivity and is a social response to media variable [19]. Shortening the response time to incoming messages might enhance mutual awareness and encourage students to attend to messages. Attending to messages affects the third category of indicators of social presence, open communication. To decrease the response time to incoming messages, experiment 4 investigated the use of animation to present system feedback.

In addition, the literature points out how critical social presence is to student performance in learning [20, 21]. This informs the design of a model for enhancing social presence, where social presence is affected by the number of interactions, the presence of others, and response time, and where social presence improves performance.

4.2. Interaction and social presence in online learning

Last section has discussed some of the potential advantages of social interaction in an online learning environment. Enabling means for social interaction in an online learning environment can provide freedom for student communication while building a Community of Inquiry. Anderson's interaction-based model of e-learning sustains the principle that an online course can be focused on student-student interaction with little loss in education effectiveness.

To increase the sense of social presence, this paper focuses on the design of the social facilities that might affect the two categories of indicators described by Garrison, Anderson and Archer [17]. The category of group cohesion might be affected by the design of the social information facilities. Using images, animation and text to present the others might enhance their presence and the students might feel part of a group. The category of open communication might be affected by the design of feedback facilities. Alerting students to incoming messages using animation might shorten the response time to incoming messages, enhancing mutual awareness.

Next section will begin by discussing the interface interaction model. This discussion is followed by research studies on the impact of the interface features that were identified in the interface interaction model. The first interface feature reviewed is the use of images, animation and text to convey information and the second is the use of animation to alert students to incoming messages. In addition, some design requirements and the challenges they entail are discussed. In particular, there are technical restrictions on the amount of visual detail that can be conveyed and on the distraction this information may impose. Enhancing social facilities therefore, entails a potential trade off between focused and divided attention.

5. The interface interaction model

This paper develops a theoretical model which describes means for increasing the number of interactions and for enhancing social presence in an online learning environment. This model considers Anderson's model of online learning and the variables indicated in the literature that might enhance social presence. These variables are: number of interactions, presence of others and response times. They were selected prioritising those that could affect the categories of indicators of social presence described by Garrison, Anderson and Archer [17]. Figure 1 shows the first version of the interface interaction model. The interface interaction model evolved over the course of the experiments to produce the final version presented in Figure 2.

The model identifies three interface features that enhance social facilities: images, animation and text. Images, animation and text are used to portray social information while animation is used to present system feedback. Four experiments were designed to test and validate the corresponding concepts [22-25]. Research prototypes of online learning environments were created for these experiments.

Figure. 1 Interface interaction model (first version)

Visibility was used in the second experiment to emphasise the interaction facilities. But this was not verified. The results do not suggest that visibility affects satisfaction nor that social presence might improve performance. The third experiment used two interfaces for each group of students. One interface was based on images, text and animation and the other was based on text. The students who used the visual-based interface interacted more using the instant mailing feature and web mail. In addition, there was a strong positive correlation between the exam grade points and perceived social presence. However, there was no statistical difference between the perceived social presence reported for both groups neither was there a statistical difference in satisfaction between the groups. The fourth experiment used animation to alert students about incoming messages. This study has shown that animation results in a greater number of web mail and instant mail messages. The results also indicated that the students who perceived a stronger social presence performed better. However, satisfaction was not affected by the interface design. Satisfaction might be a complex variable so that the questionnaire may not have been able to gather enough information about students' satisfaction with the interface. Another reason might be related to the fact that the students might have got used to the interface over a few weeks, neutralising any problem or dislike with the interface. In addition, the use of animation or text to alert students to incoming messages and system updates did not affect the perceived social presence. Once more the students had other face-to-face courses which might have influenced their sense of presence of others during the online meetings. In the final version of this model shown in Figure 2, the use of visibility, images, animation and text do not affect social presence. Nor does the interface design affect satisfaction.

Figure. 2 Interface interaction model (final version)

Figure 3 shows how the interface features and the use of images, animation and text affect the presence of others and the response time to incoming messages. The assumptions are that enhancing the presence of others supports group cohesion. In addition, shortening the response time to incoming messages enables open communication. The group cohesion and open communication are the categories of indicators of social presence.

Figure. 3 The approach adapting Anderson’s model of online learning to study the impact of the interface design on perceived social presence and the number of interactions

5.1 Images, animation and text

5.1.1. Perception of images

Having established that social information is important, it would be useful if it could be conveyed rapidly to students. Research has shown that certain types of images are perceived fairly rapidly. The process of abstraction results in simplified forms that are processed and assimilated more rapidly [26]. Abstract forms are perceived without effort and involuntarily because of their perceptual immediacy and generality [27]. Indeed, abstraction is used to broaden an image’s referential representationality [28]. This term refers to a scale where the end points are realistic photographs at one extreme, and purely alphanumeric information at the other. Images look like their referents while words need to be narrowed by adding modifiers.

Images might transmit social information in a more rapid way than text because the nature of images is amenable to pre-attentive processing. This means that objects within an image are distinguished automatically without any conscious effort. The same thing occurs when first looking at a word. Initially the letters are processed as shapes, and the word is then processed serially under the control of the reader’s conscious attention [28]. The degree of conscious attention that must be employed in the interpretation of the messages that a text conveys is higher for words than for images. Using abstract images to represent the virtual users might help in grouping them.

5.1.2. Grouping might facilitate perception of the online users.

Images might help perceive the relationships among virtual users, their connection duration, and location, because images have the flexibility to inform graphically while words impose a sequential structure on the information, i.e., a list. This means that images might be better able to convey spatial and conceptual relationships. In addition, based on the idea that memory for images tends to be better than memory for words,

abstract images might be remembered long after people see them which might help in group awareness [29, 30]. Furthermore, the user experience must be enjoyable, which can be achieved by the interplay between words and images.

5.1.3. The interplay between words and images

The interplay created by integrating words and images might provide a compelling experience to the user. Images can also facilitate text comprehension. Images might also arouse interest, create emotion and stimulate curiosity [6,4]. Peeck [4] grouped these characteristics of images as the affective-motivational role. She investigated this role of images in a study which found that children thought their illustrated booklets more attractive than non-illustrated text. The affective-motivational role of images might be crucial to students' satisfaction with the interface in an online course.

Conveying motion to the image might enhance its perception and its affective-motivational role, as discussed in Section 5.2.

5.1.4. The social space

The social space might better be represented using images, because images might suggest a vision of the virtual space using a metaphor. The suggestion of a virtual space is rooted in the association the user might have with their own experience in the physical world [31]. In addition, students' characteristics are crucial for any educational design environment. Although numerous students' characteristics could be considered, cognitive style is especially important because it bridges learning and visuals.

5.1.5. Cognitive style

The cognitive style of a great number of students is visual [32,6]. Cognitive styles are descriptions of characteristics chosen by students to acquire and organize information [33]. The verbal-visual dimension refers to how people organize information while thinking, either verbally or using pictures. This means that a verbaliser will tend to represent the information during thinking verbally while a visualiser (imager) will tend to represent in images. The bimodal, in the middle, tends to use either mode of representation. The visualiser will remember best what they see, and they will find tasks based on images easier [33]. Considering that visualisers prefer images and bimodals work well with text and images, the combination of well-designed images with text might result in higher satisfaction.

Results from Levie and Lentz [34] clearly indicate that students performed better with text and illustrations, than with text alone. Social information represented using images and text might therefore be better understood and remembered than using text alone. This combination might help students identify the location and connection duration of other virtual users. This impact of using this combination was evaluated in [22,24].

5.2. Animation

5.2.1. The perception of animation

Mutual awareness has been identified as crucial for enhancing social presence, so it would be important that students attend to messages. Moreover the feedback about incoming messages should be perceived promptly, as this could encourage a reply. Animation might be used as an alerting system because there is evidence that

humans are highly sensitive to motion [35]. Large, Beheshti, Breuleux and Renaud [36] state that animation helps the understanding of an idea when that idea involves motion. Therefore, students might notice events such as users changing location and connection duration by observing geometric shapes that move in simple ways. Motion is also considered an attribute of a visual object by Limoges, Ware and Knight [37]. This means that motion might be used to group distinct data points. Hence, motion can express certain kinds of relationships in data. Therefore, motion might depict the presence of virtual users. Animation might also be used to represent time, and motion might help users to group the online users. Grouping online users might facilitate the perception of the presence of the others. In this case, the visualisation of people is enhanced by situating them in a social space.

5.2.2. The effects of animation

The literature on audio-visual communication contains many references to the effects on learning that occur when animation is used to represent information. Animation may enhance descriptive and procedural text [36,38-39]. Large, Beheshti, Breuleux, & Renaud indicated that the presence of animation can help students to understand a text which outlines a series of steps that must be undertaken to achieve a goal. In addition, they suggest that animation is likely to be most effective when combined with text whose content is related to motion. Animation may concentrate attention on those aspects of a text that deal with motion.

Therefore, animation is an important visual attribute that might enhance the perception of other visual information such as system feedback and might contribute to shortening the response time to incoming messages and system updates. The use of animation to enhance social presence was developed in Fadel and Dyson [25].

6. Conclusion

The substantive contribution of this paper is the interface interaction model. The interface interaction model identifies three interface features that can affect the number of interactions as follows:

- Images;
- Text, and;
- Animation.

The use of images, animation and text to portray information about the others fosters web mail and instant mail interaction among students [24]. In addition, the use of animation providing system feedback to incoming messages contributes to an increase in the number of interactions [25]. Furthermore, the number of interactions might relate to the perceived social presence although the significance of this relationship could not be tested. Finally, there is a relationship between the perceived social presence and performance.

As Anderson [8] pointed out, all the interactions in an online learning environment are mediated. The interface mediates interaction. This paper concluded that the interface design is not passive in student-student interactions but affects the interactions and should be carefully considered in the development of online learning environments. Students' behaviour may be driven by the interface design, i.e., students might interact more, use a facility more than another, or follow a predetermined path. These findings have implications for designing online course environments where the interface design plays a crucial role in enhancing social presence.

Future work should take the approach of social software because this approach could be used to extend students' communication capabilities as it might improve mechanisms that students use to interact. Social software

includes everything from email to wikis (websites that allow users to edit the content without registration) and other communications systems that host many-to-many interactions. Social software contributions offer a model of collaborative writing in which the 'author' and the 'reader' roles are intertwined. Social software addresses problems about meeting, building communities, providing mentoring and personal learning assistance, working collaboratively and supporting complex group functions [40]. Numerous practical and collaborative uses are envisaged for social software, including education.

7. References

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